

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part IV. 2-(7-Iodo) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene Indigos and 2-(7-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-indole Indigos

Ajoy Kumar Das, Rajendra Prasad Sinha, and A. K. Sinha

7-Iodothioindoxyl has been condensed with variously substituted acenaphthenequinones and isatins to afford ten thioindigoid dyes. The dyeing shades on cotton and other properties of these dyes are reported.

The present communication deals with the study of 7-iodothioindigoid dyes with the object of comparing these dyes with isomeric 5-iodothioindigoid dyes, described earlier¹.

Four new dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 7-iodothioindoxyl² with acenaphthenequinone and its 3-chloro, 3-bromo, 3:4-dinitro derivatives, affording respectively the following compounds: 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene indigo (IA), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro) acenaphthylene indigo (IB), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo) acenaphthylene indigo (IC), and 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro) acenaphthylene indigo (ID). These compounds have the general formula (I).

Six other dyes 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-3'-indole indigo (R_1), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-chloro) indole indigo (R_2), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo) indole indigo (R_3), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-iodo) indole indigo (R_4), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5':7'-dibromo) indole indigo (R_5), 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro) indole indigo (R_6), have been prepared by the condensation of 7-iodothioindoxyl with isatin and its substituted products. These compounds have the general formula (R).

These dyes are soluble in pyridine, aniline, and nitrobenzene. The solution of the dyes in concentrated sulphuric acid produces characteristic colour and the original dyes

1. Sinha, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 161; 1964, 31, 463.

2. Dukunikhin and Gerasimenko, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1960, 30, 1987.

are reprecipitated unchanged on dilution of the acid solutions. The colour of the vat obtained by reduction with alkaline hydrosulphite at 50-60° is violet (acenaphthene.

quinone series) and either a yellow or greenish yellow (isatin series) from which the original colour is developed on cotton.

The absorption maxima of these dyes were determined in pyridine solution (Table I).

TABLE I

*Dye.	Shade on cotton	λ_{max}	log ϵ .
2-(7-Iodo) T-AI	Reddish violet	5180 Å	4.054
2-(5-Iodo) T-AI	Orange-red	5275	4.259
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	Reddish violet	5200	4.080
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	Violet-red	5280	4.360
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo) AI	Deep reddish violet	5200	4.080
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo) AI	Orange-red	5280	4.116
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-(3':4'-dinitro) AI	Dark reddish violet	5220	4.035
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3':4'-dinitro) AI	Blackish brown	5320	4.597
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-B	Violet-red	5080	3.984
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-B	Do	5175	3.904
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-chloro)B	Do	5050	4.030
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-chloro) B	Do	5180	3.360
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo)B	Do	5050	4.058
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo)B	Do (dark)	5190	3.408
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-iodo) B	Do (deep)	5020	4.039
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-iodo)B	Reddish violet	5220	4.000
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(6':7'-dibromo)B	Red	5080	4.080
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(6':7'-dibromo)B	Dark violet-red	5210	3.799
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro)B	Dark red	5025	4.352
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro)B	Brownish red	5290	3.490

*T=Thionaphthene

AI=Acenaphthylene indigo

B=Indole indigo

In the acenaphthenequinone series there is a bathochromic shift in absorption maxima when chlorine and bromine are substituted in the 3'-position. The 2-(7-iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)acenaphthylene indigo absorbs more powerfully than the 3'-chloro and 3'-bromo analogues. The absorption maxima of the dyes have the sequence: 3':4'-dinitro > 3'-chloro, 3'-bromo > unsubstituted,

The sequence is of the same order as in the case of 2-(5-iodo) thionaphthene-9'-acena-phthylene indigos¹ reported earlier, though the 5-iodo dyes absorb at longer wavelengths than their corresponding 7-iodo analogues, under report.

The value of molar extinction co-efficients are in the order:

3'-Bromo > 3'-Chloro > unsubstituted > 3':4'-dinitro.

In the isatin series the order of absorption maxima is as follows: 5':7'-dibromo > 5'-chloro, 5'-bromo > unsubstituted > 5'-bromo-7'-nitro > 5'-iodo and the intensities are of the order: 5'-bromo-7'-nitro > 5':7'-dibromo > 5'-bromo > 5'-iodo > 5'-chloro > unsubstituted.

These 7-iodo substituted dyes absorb at a shorter wave length than their 5-iodo analogues.¹

Investigation on the preparation and properties of 2-(4-iodo) and 2-(6-iodo)-thiona-phthene-indole indigos and acenaphthylene indigos is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the dyes.—A solution of the required acenaphthenequinone (Table II) or isatin (Table III) and 7-iodothioindoxyl in boiling glacial acetic acid was treated with HCl (Conc., 2 ml) when the product immediately separated. The reaction mixture was refluxed for further 10 to 15 min., filtered while hot, and the residue washed with a little acetic acid and hot water. The dyes were recrystallised from xylene (acenaphthenequinone series) and from nitrobenzene (isatin series).

TABLE II

Dyes	Reactants.	Appearance.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	Analysis	
						Found.	Reqd.
IA	Acenaphthenequinone (0.384 g.)+K(0.552 g.)+ AcOH (40 ml)	Foliated needles,	0.73g.	> 315°	C ₂₀ H ₈ O ₂ IS	I: 28.74% S: 7.1	28.85% 7.27
IB	3-Chloroacenaphthene- quinone (0.27 g.)+ K(0.345 g.)+AcOH (20ml)	Small granu- lar crystals	0.4g.	302°-303° (shrinking) at 290°	C ₂₀ H ₆ O ₂ ClS	Cl: 7.7 I: 28.9	7.5 28.7
IC	3-Bromoacenaphthene- quinone (0.523 g.)+K(0.552 g.) +AcOH (25 ml)	Do	0.8g.	298°-297°	C ₂₀ H ₆ O ₂ BrIS	Br+I: 40.0 S: 6.05	39.88 6.16
ID	3:4-Dinitroacenaph- thenequinone (0.544 g.) +K(0.552 g.)+AcOH (35 ml)	Rectangular plates	0.35g.	> 310°	C ₂₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ IS	I: 23.85 S: 5.8.	23.96 6.08

N.B.—T = Thionaphthene;

K = 7-Iodothioindoxyl

TABLE III

Dyes	Reagents	Appearance	Yield	M.P.	Colour in (Conc.) H_2SO_4	Formula	Found.	Reqd.
R ₁	Iastin (0.24 g.) + L (0.46 g.) + AcOH (30 ml)	Clusters of long needles	0.56g.	301-302°	Violet	$C_{16}H_8O_2NIS$	I: 31.25% S: 7.6	31.4% 7.9
R ₂	5-Chloroisatin (0.363 g.) + L(0.662 g.) + AcOH (15 ml)	Bundles of small needles	0.8g.	305-306°	Do	$C_{16}H_7O_2NClIS$	Cl: 8.0 I: 29.1 S: 7.2	8.1 28.9 7.3
R ₃	5-Bromoisatin (0.452 g.) + L(0.552 g.) + AcOH (20 ml)	Fine needles	0.71g.	> 310°	Do	$C_{16}H_7O_2NBrIS$	Br: 16.4 I: 26.0 S: 6.7	16.5 26.2 6.8
R ₄	5-Iodoisatin (0.478 g.) + L(0.503 g.) + AcOH (25 ml)	Long stout needles	0.88g.	> 310°	Do	$C_{16}H_7O_2NI_2S$	I: 24.1 S: 6.0	23.91 6.02
R ₅	5:7-Dibromoisatin (0.4 g.) + L(0.414 g.) + AcOH (30 ml)	Small needles	0.71 g	> 310°	Dirty green	$C_{16}H_6O_2NIBr_2S$	Br: 28.2 I: 22.5 S: 5.8	28.4 22.6 5.7
R ₆	5-Bromo-7-nitroisatin (0.336 g.) + L(0.345 g.) + AcOH (20 ml)	Clusters of long hair-like needles	0.5g.	> 310°	Blue	$C_{16}H_6O_4N_2BrIS$	Br: 15.0 I: 24.1 S: 6.1	15.1 24.0 6.0

N.B.—T=Thionaphthene; L=7-Iodothionidoxy.

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